

THE PROCESS OF UNDERSTANDING A LITERARY TEXT AS THE INTEGRATION OF MENTAL ACTIVITY AND MENTAL ACTION

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Abstract. this article deals with the process of understanding a literary text as the integration of mental activity and mental action. In addition, author provides several notions prominent linguists concerning understanding a literary text and experts who contributed in the sphere of literary text.

Keywords: mental activity, mental action, integration, understanding, interpretation, cognitive units, cognitive structures.

At present, as modern and up-to-date directions in the study of the literary text, the study of interpretation, linguistics, literary text of the universe, as well as communication of culture is on the field. In particular, attention is paid to the study of composing and interpretation of literary text in various genres, which allows us to present the specifics of the structure of a literary text, the main methods of text construction and text perception.

Currently, in philological hermeneutics, understanding is considered either as a process of mental activity or as a process of mental action [1].

Under my activity is understood any mental operation aimed at the discretion of the meanings of a literary text.

According to G. P. Shchedrovitsky, any process taking place in thinking “is primarily an activity for the development of new knowledge. This activity highlights a certain content in the general <context> of reality” [1]. In this case, the following is not interpreted as a separate concept, but is only considered as “the principle of universality of logical formulas of thinking” [1].

G.I. Bogin points out that mental activity is the “intentionality of consciousness [2]. According to G. I. Bogin, consciousness in this definition is equal to thinking. The terms “mental activity” is not differentiated, but is used in the description of mental activity. Note that our activity is always characterized by directionality, and directionality is that intention (from Lat. Yepeo - to stretch, stretch, direct), which allows thinking to perform both a categorical function and a function of formal inference. The existing concepts of “intention”, “intentionality” are considered as a characteristic of thinking or one of the ways of thinking. Thus, within the framework of E. Husserl’s phenomenological philosophy, intentionality is a “possible way of realizing an object”, which is

divided into a number of types such as “possible perception, retention, memory, expectation, signification, contemplation by analogy” [3]. Analyzing the original Latin unit “Mepyo”, G. I. Bogin emphasizes: “The language itself has already said that turning to an object is an indication, rather, something alive or similar to living, since it was precisely itentio, not ostentio, more often used in the sense of indicating inanimate or not so alive” [2].

In this dissertation, it is indicated that the process of mental activity as a process of understanding one's own actions always occurs directionally, i.e. intentionally. If the proposed work explores the process of understanding and interpreting material texts, then there is a need to comprehend both our actions, and the steps between these actions, and how this comprehension occurs.

Our actions in the process of understanding and interpretation are represented by activated representations and cognitive structures. Therefore, in this article, the process of understanding and interpreting a literary text is analyzed as the integration of my activity and my action.

By my following is understood the recipient's comprehension of his mental actions.

Under my action - the actions of the recipient with activated representations.

For example, the recipient, reading the following sentence from the novel by I. S. Turgenev “Fathers and Children”: “Peter, who, as an improved servant, did not approach the handle of the master, but only bowed to him from afar, disappeared under the gate again”, comprehends the perceived ideas about the author’s irony (represented in the description of the servant), about the new relationship between the servant and the master. Such comprehension begins with the recipient comprehending the lexical means by which he saw the idea of the author’s irony. In this case, such a means will be the use of the word “improved”, which the author characterizes the servant. The idea of a new relationship between servants and the owner is seen due to the indication of the fact that the “improved servant” did not approach the handle of the barich. It is this idea that is seen for the reason that the recipient knows about the changes in society at the historical moment that is described in the novel (the years before the abolition of serfdom, when the servants already had some freedom and got out from under the full power of the owner). Actions with these ideas (about the author's irony and about the new relationship between servants and master) will be not an action, but an understanding of these actions (i.e. my

activity) will be the answers to the questions: “What is being comprehended?”, “What ideas are being seen?” and “Why are such representations seen?”.

Integration (as a process that results in integrity) is manifested in the fact that the process of mental action (as actions with representations) can occur without mental activity (i.e., without understanding one's actions), but mental activity without mental action is impossible, because understanding actions is the understanding of movement from one representation to another.

The advantage of the approach to the process of understanding as an integration of mental activity and mental action is that it allows, on the one hand, to identify cognitive units and cognitive structures functioning in the process of understanding, on the other hand, to describe the mechanism of the process of understanding and interpretation of a literary text.

If our activity is the comprehension of our actions, then in the process of such comprehension there is a need to identify the links between the steps of these actions. And the identification of connections is possible only through understanding one's own way of categorizing activated cognitive units and formed cognitive structures. Consequently, the comprehension of actions in the process of reception of a literary text directly concerns the problem of cognitive structures. The study of cognitive structures, in turn, involves the calculation of cognitive units from which cognitive structures are formed. If cognitive units are identified, then the question arises about how structures are formed from these units. The answer to such a question implies a description of the mechanism of the understanding process. The description of the mechanism of understanding and interpretation of artistic text reveals the stability of connections between cognitive units and cognitive structures and is a model of understanding and interpretation. The stability of connections is conditioned by such a unity of the thinking system of all mankind, which is characterized by “basic forms of thinking” [4]. Therefore, when studying the process of understanding, it is necessary to “focus on thinking as an object” [5]. The approach to the process of understanding as an integration of our activity and our action reveals both the steps of understanding and the structural connections in the process of understanding. At the same time, there is a need to distinguish between the concepts of “system” and “structure”. This is due to the fact that “although the concepts of system, function, structure, component are common to many sciences, they are interpreted differently in different branches of knowledge” [6].

A system (from the Greek systema - whole) is the union of some diversity into a single and clearly dissected whole, the elements of which, in relation to the whole and other parts, occupy the corresponding months, and the structure (from the Latin structura - structure, order, connection) is a set of stable connections between the elements of an object that ensure its integrity.

The difference between the proposed approach to the process of understanding from other approaches is that it involves the identification of cognitive units and cognitive structures that the recipient operates in the process of understanding and interpreting a literary text.

The identification of cognitive units and cognitive structures shows that the totality of knowledge about the world in the linguistic consciousness is structured in a certain way [7], is “packaged” in a certain way. In the present study, the totality of knowledge is understood as the sum of mnemonic units of knowledge, the connection between which is not accidental, since the violation of this connection or its disappearance (for some reason) leads to a change in the entire structure, i.e. “structurality can take place only if there are connections” [8].

If the whole process of understanding is presented as a complex object, then this object appears as a set of elements or units that can be relied upon as:

- a) heterogeneous, and then the composition is characterized only by “quality”,
- b) homogeneous in a certain respect, and then the composition also receives quantitative characteristics.

The object can be interpreted as lattice of connected elements or units, in this case, the study “should take precedence relationships between elements of the object and the object itself”, and understanding is seen as an “object from its structure and content” [1].

In the present work is to identify the units that make up the structure of the investigated object and the object itself in the form of integration of thought-activity and maledictory.

In the process of understanding, only such individual MEZ are activated that contribute to the discretion of the presentation. Experimental confirmation of this hypothesis can be found in the works of M.S. Shechter, V.G. Stepanov. It was found that the process of understanding does not require the obligatory registration of all the features of the object. It is possible to create an image based on a few “strong” features. “The structural basis of creative processes is

the selective nature of the image, the discrete principle of perception and transformation of reality” [9].

The stability of connections between cognitive units and cognitive structures is explained either as subordination of personality to the “influence of archetypes”, or as subordination of personality to the unity of the logical thinking system. At the same time, the system of rules governing the act of understanding acts as a language as a way of translating the plan of expression of the text into the plan of content and vice versa, i.e. as a decryption mechanism. This translation is associated with the procedure of understanding, in the process of which “the personality obeys the requirements of thinking as a social institution” [10] The language thus acts as a way of establishing understanding and its practical implementation. “That's why the text always fixes the structure of understanding”. In this case, the difference between structure and system is obvious, since “structure is what is immanently inherent in the object itself, and the system is the organization of the object, ideally set in such a way as to best represent the object” [11]. Strictly speaking, the structure is a creation of nature, the system is a creation of man.

If the process of understanding is considered as subordination of the personality to the “influence of archetypal representations” (Pauli, 1975: 137), then the concept of “archetype” means stable psychological schemes (figures), psychological prerequisites and possibilities of images (Jung, 1988). They are unconscious, a priori, super individual in nature. Archetypes are the content of the “collective unconscious”, which is the universal basis of everyday life and is identical for all people. According to C. Jung, all the most significant ideas, important points of view go back to the archetypes of the collective unconscious. Within the framework of the Jungian tradition, eternal, universal archetypes in myths, beliefs, dreams, in works of literature and art are identified and studied. In the analysis of cultural phenomena, social memory, there are such expressions as “shadow archetype”, “bonfire archetype”, “city archetype”, “holiday archetype”, “father archetype”, etc.

Archetypal representations and the unity of the structure of the logical thinking of all mankind are characterized by equal signs of the structural “packaging” of the knowledge received. And if “archetypal representations, images, schemes existing in the deep layers of thinking, implicitly form our worldview, worldview and rational concepts, ideas, logically dissected, clearly realized, explicitly expressed, socially articulated”, then the unity of the logical thinking system is conditioned by the same characteristics. For example, the

“archetype of time” underlies our “empirical experiences and perceptions of time” [12].

I. Kant considers the unity of the logical thinking system or the subordination of the individual to the requirements of thinking as a social institution as acting according to schemes. Thus, according to I. Kant, reason has the idea of the form of the whole in advance, a priori, in other words, initially, before experience, or rather, outside of any experience; reason assumes that there is a unity of the manifold (the concept of “mind”, according to I. Kant, is considered as the concept of “thinking”. This idea of the form of the whole of knowledge precedes certain knowledge of parts and contains the conditions for a priori determining the place of any part and its relation to other parts. Thus, this idea postulates a complete unity of rational knowledge, thanks to which this knowledge is not a random aggregate, but a system connected according to the necessary laws. This is not a concept of an object, but an idea that we relate to nature, considering our knowledge insufficient if it is not adequate to the idea. However, I. Kant did not deny that consistency is inherent in nature itself. At the same time, reason, according to Kant, systematizes phenomena, not nature. Thus, thinking, according to I. Kant, stands as a system. In this work, the theory of I. Kant on the schematism of the process of understanding is taken as a basis. He considers the interaction with the representations of appearance, object, nature as a manifestation of schematism of thinking. Such schematism of thinking in the process of understanding each artist's text both in his native and in a foreign language has a number of achievements that are associated with his individual past experience, culture. The discrepancies revealed in the generalized pictures of the world among representatives of different linguistic and cultural communities can lead “to the formation of a misunderstanding of a foreign cultural literary text” [13].

If, in the process of understanding, a person submits to the requirements of thinking as a social institution, then in the process of interpretation it is impossible to go beyond the content of the text.

The approach proposed in this paper to the process of understanding as the integration of mental activity and mental action must be viewed as a “product of a certain point of view” [14], which allows analyzing the subject in the chosen perspective.

The advantage of the approach to the process of understanding as a process of integration of mental activity and mental action is that it allows you to identify cognitive units and cognitive structures that function in the process of

understanding and on the basis of the identified cognitive units and cognitive structures to justify the possibility of multiple interpretations. Identification of cognitive units, and cognitive

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